

Alleviating Urban Heat Island: The Roles of Architects and Town Planners

¹Onugha Christian Ugochukwu ²Michael C. Oguike ³Ifiok Enobong Mfon and ⁴Ndifreke Moses Etim

¹Department of Architecture, Imo State University, Owerri, Nigeria. Onugha.chris2013@gmail.com

²Department of Architecture, University Uyo, Nigeria. michaeloguike@uniuyo.edu.ng

³Department of Architecture, University Uyo, Nigeria. ifiokifiokifiok@gmail.com.

⁴Department of Urban and Regional Planning, University of Uyo. etim_ndifreke@yahoo.com

Abstract

Urban Heat Island (UHI) is a phenomenon characterized by elevated temperatures within urban areas compared to their rural surroundings, poses significant challenges to the environment, public health, infrastructure, and energy consumption. This paper provides an overview of UHI, its effects on urban environments, and mitigation strategies. UHI manifests due to factors such as reduced vegetation, increased heat-absorbing materials, and human activities, exacerbating air pollution and health risks. Studies indicate correlations between land use patterns and UHI distribution, highlighting the importance of green spaces in mitigating UHI effects. Mitigation strategies including reforestation, cool roofs, and reflective pavements are crucial for reducing UHI intensity and improving urban resilience. Integration of these strategies into urban planning frameworks is essential for sustainable development. Addressing UHI as part of broader urban climate resilience efforts emphasizes the importance of green infrastructure, sustainable design practices, community engagement, and innovative policies for creating healthier and more sustainable urban environments.

Key words: Urban Heat Island (UHI), urban climate resilience, green infrastructure and sustainable design,

1) Introduction

Urban heat Island refers to the increase of air temperature in the near-surface layer of the atmosphere within cities relative to their surrounding countryside (Balogun, Balogun and Adeyewa, 2012). Urban heat island (UHI) is a well-known negative effect of urbanization resulting in higher air temperatures in urban centres than in the surrounding rural areas (Li et al, 2019). Urban heat island is an area that is significantly warmer than its surrounding rural areas due to human activities. The temperature difference is usually larger at night than during the day (Ebuga, Datukun, and Obadiah, 2023).

UHIs manifest when urban areas become notably warmer than their rural surroundings due to factors such as reduced vegetation, increased heat-absorbing materials, and waste heat from human activities. The impact of Urban Heat Island (UHI) can be examined through various indicators such as the Heat and Humidity Index (THI), Land Surface Temperature (LST), the Related Stress Index (RSI), and the frequency of Beer Garden days (Yang, Qian, Song and Zheng, 2016). This phenomenon is not only detrimentally to the environment but also poses risks to human health. Studies have shown that common health issues associated with UHI

include digestive problems, as well as neurological disorders like memory impairment, depression, irritability, and insomnia (Irfeey, Jamei, Chau and Ramasubramanian, 2023; Isioye, Ikwueze and Akomolafe, 2020).

Moreover, the thermal influence of UHI can lead to the circulation of pollution, causing local winds to carry urban-contaminated air from suburban to urban areas, exacerbating urban air pollution and imposing financial burdens on city dwellers. Factors such as the layout of buildings, their orientation, and spacing influence the absorption of solar radiation by urban surfaces (Van der Meulen *et al.*, 2020). The arrangement of buildings significantly impacts the distribution of shadows and temperature variations across a city. Various factors, including the thermal properties, colour, texture, and coverage of urban surface materials, influence urban heat exchange (Santamouris and Yun, 2020). The scarcity of vegetation in urban regions amplifies heat absorption by structures like buildings, pavements, and roads. Human activities such as driving and HVAC (heat, ventilation, and air conditioning) systems further contribute to atmospheric heat build-up. The UHI effect is typically assessed at three levels: ground level, canopy level, and urban level (Sabrin *et al.*, 2021). Responses to the effect of UHIs can be categorized as either adaptation or mitigation. Adaptations are made to decrease the harm, whereas mitigation is an activity performed to lessen the intensity or amount of the effect. The UHI effect can be adapted to and mitigated at the building, neighbourhood, municipal, and regional levels (Irfeey *et al.*, 2023).

2) Urban Heat Island in Nigerian Cities

According to the findings by Isioye, Ikwueze, and Akomolafe (2020), changes in urban thermal field variance index (UTFVI) distribution were closely linked to the expansion of urban areas during the period from 2009 to 2019 in Abuja, Nigeria. The study, which utilized data extracted from Landsat 8 OLI/TIRS imagery, Band 10, it established that there was variability in UHI distribution within the Abuja Municipal Area Council (AMAC). Generally, the results indicated a temperature difference of 19°C between areas with low UHI intensity near water bodies and those with high UHI intensity in densely populated north-eastern neighbourhoods. The analysis revealed varying levels of thermal comfort. Hot spots of UTFVI were predominantly observed in built-up areas, particularly densely populated and commercial districts, indicating susceptibility to UHI.

Furthermore, the correlation analysis conducted between retrieved Land surface temperature (LST), Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI), and Normalized Difference Built-up Index (NDBI) indicated that green spaces could mitigate the urban heat island effect, whereas built-up areas could exacerbate it. The distribution of UHI phenomena appeared to be directly related to the city's land use and land cover distribution. While woodlands, urban parks, and green spaces had a mitigating effect on UHI, densely populated areas, industrial zones, and large train stations intensified it. Approximately 72% of the city's landscape maintained a normal microclimate for living, which was positive. However, approximately 11.25% of the city exhibited unfavourable heat stress conditions, suggesting potential impacts of the UHI phenomenon on urban quality of life, particularly in north-western neighbourhoods and small pockets in the south and southeast.

Origho (2016) adopted empirical and exposit facto research survey using integrated remote sensing and geographic information system to identify landuse/landcover types in Warri metropolis, including their temporal transformation and association with land surface temperatures from the landsat TM and landsat ETM imageries of 1987, 2001, 2009, and 2011 respectively. It was found that as the built-up area increased in size, so did the land surface temperature. Increased in built up areas was found to be a key determinant for the rise in mean Land surface temperature from 1987 to 2011. The analysis indicated a 3.30°C temperature increase. Additionally, a direct relationship between the changing pattern among the various landuse/landcover types and the variations in the surface temperatures of these landuse/landcover types within the period of study was revealed.

Zitta and Akinseye (2020) examined the different land cover in the urban area of Jos for three decades and also assessed the UHI associated with the land cover types. Composed images were ordered into four area classes: water, built-up, bare-surface and vegetation. NDVI, Land Use Land Cover and Land Surface Temperature were used for the study. Findings in 1985 indicated that, the dominant land use was bare-surface, vegetation occupied the largest area in 2000, in 2017, built-up area occupied the largest proportion of the land area. Most extensive UHI occurred in the central part of the CBD which was Terminus in 1985, in 2000, spots of UHI were observed in Bukuru area South of the metropolis. In the year 2017, there was an enormous widespread of urban heat island from the city centre of Jos to the North and North-East of the metropolis. Variation of temperature between different land cover for the year 2000 indicated that built-up area had the highest average temperature of 27.68⁰C and the highest temperature was observed in the built-up areas with an average of 29.52⁰C in 2017 as against 24.84⁰C observed in 1985 showing an increase of 2.7⁰C.

3) Conceptual Framework: Urban Climate Resilience

Urban Climate Change Resilience (UCCR) refers to the ability of cities to manage the threats an increasingly urban population faces due to climate change and associate risks. But beyond its core agenda of dealing with climate change, UCCR also presents cities with an incredible opportunity to tackle existing failures of urban development (Asian Development Bank, 2014). Awareness of the importance of city resilience as a critical urban development agenda is growing, as are the benefits of investing in resilience. In the international development community we used to speak in terms of planning for disaster risk reduction (DRR). Now resilience means looking at ways cities can withstand, adapt and transform, staying focused on long-term benefits rather than short-term fixes. Rather than focusing on single threats, UCCR recognizes that climate change may result in a wide range of hazards, which it's impossible to predict. It addresses risk as part of a wider agenda emphasizing the importance of inclusive governance and integrated planning. The governance issue is key. If cities are to become truly resilient, the population must have a voice: consultation breeds better long-term decision making.

UCCR represents a maturation of the climate change agenda. In the last decade the climate change sceptics have finally been silenced, not just by the growing evidence base, but by cities across the world responding to the real change they're experiencing locally. The agreement signed at COP21 in Paris in December 2015, cemented this realisation as a global

agenda. And given cities are now projected to house 70% of the world's population by 2050, they have become central to the debate which has understandably shifted to adaptation and mitigation. The work of the C40 cities and the Compact of Mayors are testament to cities recognizing the critical role they play in tackling climate change.

UCCR's breadth of perspective is a key strength, focusing on 'the ability of cities to persist in the face of the multiple threats posed by climate change'. Today, UCCR embraces the capacity of cities to prepare for and withstand sudden shocks familiar from disaster risk reduction thinking. It also focuses the need to adapt progressively as stresses accumulate. Finally, it is able to identify the opportunities pressures provide to think differently, adopt new strategies and transform. The most exciting part about UCCR's momentum is its role as a paradigm shift, one that takes us beyond 'development as usual'. Development has typically focused on economic growth and prosperity, at the expense of social inclusion or sustainable development. UCCR inherently recognises that within a city, climate change impacts are experienced unequally, and it challenges cities to engage in collective action that benefits all.

UHIs are recognized as a significant climate-related challenge that demands proactive measures to enhance the adaptability and sustainability of urban environments. Town planners, by embracing roles such as Green Infrastructure Champions, Sustainable Design Advocates, Community Engagement Facilitators, and Policy and Innovation Drivers, contribute to building urban resilience against the escalating threat of UHIs (Sharma and Singh, 2013). The concept of Urban Climate Resilience underscores the importance of integrating green infrastructure, sustainable design practices, community engagement, and innovative policies to enhance a city's ability to withstand and recover from the impacts of increased temperatures associated with UHIs. It emphasizes a holistic approach that considers the interconnectedness of urban systems and the well-being of the community in the face of changing climate patterns.

4) Effects of Urban Heat Island

The Urban Heat Island (UHI) effect, characterized by higher temperatures in urban areas compared to their rural surroundings, manifests in various consequences impacting both the environment and public well-being. Elevated temperatures within urban environments, particularly noticeable at night, constitute the primary outcome of UHI. This thermal disparity poses a range of effects on urban ecosystems and inhabitants. One significant concern associated with UHI is the potential health risks it introduces. The increased heat stress in urban areas can contribute to heat-related illnesses, posing a particular threat to vulnerable populations such as the elderly, children, and individuals with pre-existing health conditions. Furthermore, the UHI effect drives up energy consumption, especially for cooling purposes like air conditioning, leading to heightened demand on power grids and potential increases in greenhouse gas emissions.

The degradation of air quality is another consequence linked to UHI. The trapped pollutants in the urban air can result in the formation of smog, negatively impacting respiratory health and overall air quality. Additionally, UHI contributes to water stress as higher temperatures increase evaporation rates, intensifying the demand for water resources, which can exacerbate existing water scarcity challenges in urban areas. Beyond its direct impact on human health

and resources, UHI influences local weather patterns, potentially altering wind patterns, precipitation distribution, and overall atmospheric conditions. This can create microclimates within urban environments, affecting the ecosystems and biodiversity of the region. Infrastructure stress is another facet, with higher temperatures accelerating wear and tear on structures.

5) Mitigation of Urban Heat Islands

The implementation of various mitigation strategies such as reforestation, the adoption of green and cool roofs, and the utilization of cool pavements are crucial steps in combating the Urban Heat Island (UHI) effect. These strategies not only mitigate the adverse effects of UHI but also contribute significantly to energy savings and the reduction of greenhouse gas emissions. Moreover, they play a vital role in improving public health outcomes by minimizing heat-related risks. Additionally, integrating these strategies into urban planning processes is essential for both current and future urban development (Spronken-Smith and Oke, 1998). To effectively incorporate these mitigation measures, it is imperative to assess the city's landscape and planning frameworks, particularly focusing on the relationships between land use, land cover, and surface temperatures. This detailed analysis serves as a foundation for the development of urban planning schemes that prioritize climate change adaptation.

Increasing green spaces within urban areas emerges as a pivotal mitigation measure. These green spaces not only act as wind barriers but also intercept solar radiation, thereby reducing air temperatures through evapo-transpiration (Scott, Simpson and Mcpherso, 1999). Studies suggest that such interventions can lower air temperatures by significant margins, ranging from 1.6°C to 3.3°C. Furthermore, vegetated areas facilitate groundwater recharge and effectively control surface temperature rise, a phenomenon also observed in the case of green roofs. Meanwhile, the adoption of reflective or "cool" roofs, characterized by high albedo and emissivity properties, stands out as an effective UHI mitigation strategy. Enhancing the albedo of roofs can substantially reduce ambient temperatures. For instance, a mere increase of 0.07 in albedo on building and road surfaces can lead to a temperature decrease of up to 2°C (Villanueva-Solis, 2017). Similarly, reducing solar radiation absorption by roads and parking lots can result in a notable reduction in peak air temperatures.

Green roofs offer multifaceted benefits including shading, air temperature reduction via evapo-transpiration, and mitigation of building thermal loads. Moreover, their thermal mass property contributes to regulating inner surface temperatures over time, distinguishing them as efficient solutions for mitigating UHI effects. In this regards, Architects should rethink their choice and usage of building materials, as they do have influence on the temperature of a locale.

6) Conclusion

Urban Heat Island (UHI) poses significant challenges to urban environments, characterized by elevated temperatures within cities compared to their rural surroundings. This phenomenon not only impacts the environment but also poses risks to public health, strains infrastructure, and exacerbates energy consumption and air pollution. However, proactive measures can be taken to mitigate the adverse effects of UHI. Mitigation strategies such as

reforestation, the adoption of green and cool roofs, and the utilization of cool pavements are crucial steps in combating UHI. These strategies not only help reduce the urban heat island effect but also contribute to energy savings, greenhouse gas emissions reduction, and improved public health outcomes. Integrating these strategies into urban planning processes is essential for current and future urban development.

Increasing green spaces within urban areas acts as a pivotal mitigation measure by reducing air temperatures through evapo-transpiration and facilitating groundwater recharge. Reflective or "cool" roofs, with high albedo and emissivity properties, effectively reduce ambient temperatures when adopted. Similarly, green roofs offer multiple benefits including shading, air temperature reduction, and mitigation of building thermal loads. By implementing these mitigation strategies and integrating them into urban planning frameworks, cities can enhance their resilience against the escalating threat of UHI. This holistic approach, emphasizing green infrastructure, sustainable design practices, community engagement, and innovative policies, underscores the importance of addressing UHI as part of broader urban climate resilience efforts. Ultimately, proactive measures against UHI are essential for creating healthier, more sustainable, and resilient urban environments for present and future generations.

Architects and town planners play crucial roles in mitigating the Urban Heat Island (UHI) effect through collaborative efforts in urban design and planning. Architects focus on designing buildings with green features, cool roofing technologies, and passive design strategies that reduce heat absorption and promote thermal comfort. They integrate green spaces, vegetated facades, and shading devices into their designs to mitigate UHI within the built environment. Town planners complement these efforts by implementing zoning regulations that prioritize green infrastructure, transit-oriented development, and sustainable land use patterns. They design urban green infrastructure plans, promote transit accessibility, and engage communities in participatory planning processes to foster sustainable urban development. Through their collective expertise, architects and town planners contribute to creating resilient, livable, and environmentally sustainable cities that mitigate the adverse effects of UHI and enhance urban quality of life.

References

- AbuBakr, M., Ebrahimpour, M., Asadpoor, A. and Asadi, S. M. (2023). Analysis of Two Decades Variations in Urban Heat Island Using Remotely Sensed Data in Nguru Local Government Area, Yobe State, Nigeria. *Journal of Sustainable Agriculture and Environment*, 24(1), 37-49.
- Balogun, I., Balogun, A. and Adeyewa, Z. (2011) Observed urban heat Island characteristics in Akure, Nigeria. *African Journal of Environmental Science and Technology* Vol. 6(1), pp. 1-8.
- Ebuga, E., Datukun, H. and Bashayi, O. (2023) Evolving Green Areas Planning Strategies as A Means of Mitigating Urban Heat Island in Lafia Town, Nasarawa State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Latest Technology in Engineering, Management and Applied Science* 12 (8) 112-124.
- Etim, N., Ivo, H. and Eteng, S.(2023). Residential Area Dissonance in Ikot Ekpene Urban, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Engineering Inventions*12 (4)333-339.

- Etim, N., Ivo, H. and Adiasenam, U. (2023). Planning Implications of Land Use Change in Ikot Ekpene LGA Nigeria. *International Journal of Urban Planning and Developmental Studies* 1(2) 46-50
- George, B., Mfon, E. and Etim, N. (2024). Development and Utilization of Nanotechnology in Medicine and the Built Environment. *International Journal of Development, Sustainability and Environmental Management* 4 (2) pp 6-13.
- Irfeey, A.M.M.; Chau, H.-W.; Sumaiya, M.M.F.; Wai, C.Y.; Muttill, N.; Jamei, E.(2023). Sustainable Mitigation Strategies for Urban Heat Island Effects in Urban Areas. *Sustainability* 15(10767) 1-26. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su151410767>.
- Isioye, O., Ikwueze, H. and Akomolafe, E. (2020). Urban Heat Island Effects and Thermal Comfort in Abuja Municipal Area Council of Nigeria. *FUTY Journal of the Environment Vol. 14 (2) 19-34*.
- Ivo, H. and Etim, N. (2023). Environmental Perspectives on Wetland Degradation in Itu LGA, Nigeria. *International Journal of Developmental Studies and Environmental Monitoring* 2(2) 45-50.
- Li, D., Liao, W., Rigden, A. J., Liu, X., Wang, D., Malyshev, S., Shevliakova, E. (2019). Urban heat island: Aerodynamics or imperviousness? *Sci. Adv.*, 5, eaau4299.
- Lynn, B.H., Carlson, T.N., Rosenzweig, C., Goldberg, R., Druyan, L., Cox, J., Gaffin, S., Parshall, L. and Civerolo, K. (2009) A Modification to the NOAA LSM to Simulate Heat Mitigation Strategies in the New York City Metropolitan Area. *Journal of Applied Meteorology and Climatology*, 48.
- Mfon, I. Oguike, M. and Ossom, U. (2024). Creating Tomorrow: An Innovative Guide for Sustainable Architectural Design. *International Journal of Development, Sustainability and Environmental Management* 4 (2) 26-36.
- Mfon, I. and Etim, N. (2023). Harmonizing Aesthetics, Sustainability, and Post-Disaster Resilience: A Holistic Approach in Contemporary Architecture. *International Journal of Development, Sustainability and Environmental Management* 3(1) pp 15-20.
- Mfon, I., George, B. and Etim, N. (2024). Advancing Sustainability in Industrial Buildings: Materials and Construction Practices. *International Journal of Developmental Studies and Environmental Monitoring* 1(1) 1-7.
- Ojo, E. O. (2017). Urban Heat Island Effects in Akure, Ondo State, Nigeria. *Journal of Environmental Geography*, 10(4), 1-12.
- Origho, T. (2016). Examination of the Spatial Characteristics Of Urban Heat Island In Warri Metropolis, Delta State, Nigeria. Doctoral dissertation, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka. 116p.
- Sabrin, S.; Karimi, M.; Nazari, R.; Pratt, J.; Bryk, J. (2021). Effects of Different Urban-Vegetation Morphology on the Canopy-Level Thermal Comfort and the Cooling Benefits of Shade Trees: Case-Study in Philadelphia. *Sustain. Cities Soc.* 66, 102684.
- Santamouris, M.; Yun, G.Y. Recent Development and Research Priorities on Cool and Super Cool Materials to Mitigate Urban Heat Island. *Renew. Energy* 2020, 161, 792–807.
- Scott, K.I., Simpson, J.R. and McPherson, E.G. (1999) Effects of Tree Cover on Parking Lot Microclimate and Vehicle Emissions. *Journal of Arboriculture*, 25, 129-142.
- Sharma, D and Singh, R. (2013). Urban Climate Resilience: A Review of the Methodologies Adopted under the ACCCRN initiative in Indian cities. ACCCRN Working Paper Series 5. .

- Spronken-Smith, R.A. and Oke, T.R. (1998) The Thermal Regime of Urban Parks in Two Cities with Different Summer Climates. *International Journal of Remote Sensing*, 19, 2085-2104. <https://doi.org/10.1080/014311698214884>.
- Taha, H., Douglas, S. and Haney, J. (1997) Meso-scale Meteorological and Air Quality Impacts of Increased Urban Albedo and Vegetation. *Energy and Building*, 25, 169-177.
- Van der Meulen, E.S.; van Oel, P.R.; Rijnaarts, H.H.M.; Sutton, N.B.; van de Ven, F.H.M.(2022). Suitability Indices for Assessing Functional Quality of Urban Surface Water. *City Environ. Interact.* 13, 100079.
- Villanueva, J., Venegas, F.R. and García, O.R. (2008) Urban Heat Island: Urban Analysis, Assessment and Measuring Mitigation in Cities of Extreme Dry Weather. The 3rd International C.E.U. Congress: Climate Change and Urban Design, Oslo, 14-16 September 2008, 180-190.
- Villanueva-Solis, J. (2017) Urban Heat Island Mitigation and Urban Planning: The Case of the Mexicali, B. C. Mexico. *American Journal of Climate Change*, 6, 22-39.
- Yang, L.; Qian, F.; Song, D.X.; Zheng, K.J. (2016). Research on Urban Heat-Island Effect. *Procedia Eng.* 169, 11–18.
- Zitta, W. and Akinseye, S. (2020). Assessment of Urban Heat Island using Remote Sensing and GIS Techniques in Jos Metropolis, Nigeria. *FUDMA International Journal of Social Sciences* 2 (2) 29 – 40.

jenvironmentalmonitoring@gmail.com